

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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THE PATHOGENETIC PROCESSES BEHIND PERIODONTAL DISORDERS AND CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS**Turumova M.B.**

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Resume. To identify and treat patients at the earliest stage of the condition in order to minimize intervention costs, maintain the tooth's anatomical and functional integrity, and stop the illness from progressing further. Twenty patients were the focus of microbiologic studies on gram-negative bacilli, *Candida* fungus, epidermal staphylococcus, and non-hemolytic streptococcus. The study found that 17% of the teeth with extra canals were in the apical area, compared to 9% and 2% in the middle and upper thirds, respectively. Destructive periodontal changes associated with the canal were comparatively rare. Prior to restoring the tooth's supporting structures, the most successful therapy should concentrate on removing the microbial element from the periodont into the pocket and root canal system.

Keywords: periodontitis, bacilli, candida, fuzobacterii, paradontal tissue

ПАРОДОНТ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ ВА СУРУНКАЛИ ПЕРИОДОНТИТНИНГ АСОСИДА ЁТУВЧИ ПАТОГЕНЕТИК ЖАРАЁНЛАР**Турумова М.Б.**

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Резюме. Мақсад — аралашув харажатларини минималлаштириши, тишининг анатомик ва функционал яхлитлигини сақлаб қолиши ҳамда касалликнинг кейинги ривожланишини тўхтатиши мақсадида беморларни касалликнинг энг дастлабки босқичида аниқлаш ва даволаш. Йигирма нафар беморда грамманфий бациллар, *Candida* замбуруғлари, эпидермал стафилококklar ва негемолитик стрептококklar бўйича микробиологик тадқиқотлар ўтказилди. Тадқиқот натижаларига кўра, қўшимча каналлар апикал соҳадаги тишларнинг 17% да аниқланди, ўрта ва юқори учдан бир қисмида эса бу кўрсаткич мос равишда 9% ва 2% ни ташкил этди. Канал билан боғлиқ бўлган пародонтнинг деструктив ўзгаришлари нисбатан кам учради. Тишининг таянч тузилмаларини тиклашдан олдин, энг муваффақиятли терапия пародонтдан чўнтакка ва илдиз канали тизимида ўтган микроб элементини олиб ташлашга қаратилган бўлиши керак.

Калит сўзлар: периодонтит, бациллар (таёқчалар), кандида, фузобактериялар, пародонт тўқимаси.

ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ, ЛЕЖАЩИЕ В ОСНОВЕ ПАРОДОНТАЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ И ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПЕРИОДОНТИТА**Турумова М.Б.**

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Резюме. Целью является выявление и лечение пациентов на самой ранней стадии заболевания, чтобы минимизировать затраты на вмешательство, сохранить анатомическую и функциональную целостность зуба и остановить дальнейшее развитие болезни. Двадцать пациентов были объектом микробиологических исследований на предмет выявления грамотрицательных палочек, грибов рода *Candida*, эпидермального стафилококка и негемолитических стрептококков. Исследование показало, что дополнительные каналы были обнаружены в 17% зубов в апикальной области, по сравнению с 9% и 2% в средней и верхней трети соответственно. Деструктивные изменения пародонта, связанные с каналом, встречались сравнительно редко. Перед восстановлением опорных структур зуба наиболее успешная терапия должна быть сосредоточена на удалении микробного элемента из пародонта в карман и систему корневых каналов.

Ключевые слова: периодонтит, палочки (бациллы), кандида, фузобактерии, пародонтальная ткань.

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Annotation: The supporting tissues around the teeth are destroyed by inflammation in patients with periodontitis. Alveolar bone resorption, periodontal ligament loss, and gingival loss of collagen and connec-

tive tissue are all typical. As a result of the tooth roots being exposed to the oral environment, a bacterial biofilm is formed on the root and root cementum, which has the potential to solidify into dental calculus. This disease's chronicity and often sluggish development lead to tooth movement, loss of chewing ability, aesthetic abnormalities, and, eventually, tooth exfoliation if treatment is not received. Additionally, low-grade systemic inflammation that is induced by periodontal infection might have detrimental consequences on other organs.

Aggressive and chronic periodontitis are the two categories into which the most prevalent kinds of periodontitis have historically been divided. One It has lately been recognized, although, that this classification's scientific foundation is shaky and depends on a varied clinical presentation. [2–5] The difference between different clinical presentations has been eliminated, especially given the intricacy of the causes that cause periodontitis and will be covered in this study. 5, 6 Clinical diagnosis had many drawbacks, such as significant overlap and unclear pathobiology-based differentiations within the designated categories, diagnostic imprecision, and challenges with therapy implementation. Despite offering a practical framework that has been widely used in periodontology research and clinical practice over the last 17 years, the 1999 classification¹ was judged to have too many flaws to be of continuing use. [5, 6,] and the introduction of a new classification. [7]

Depending on the criteria used to define severe periodontitis and the particular study group examined, epidemiological research has shown that between 7% and 14% of people in western Europe and North America suffer from the condition. [8–10]. The incidence of severe periodontitis may range from 10% to 15% among populations and nations with inadequate access to dental care, poor oral health awareness, and few preventative interventions.[9] It's possible that certain racial/ethnic groups have greater genetic susceptibility factors than others; in central and east sub-Saharan Africa, as well as in some racial/ethnic groups in the United States, the frequency of severe periodontal disease was reported to be as high as 20%.[8, 9].

This pathology's high frequency, broad range of etiologic factors, large diversity of forms, and somewhat complicated and often poorly understood mechanism of illness pathogenesis are the reasons for its considerable attention. Even though the etiology, processes of development, and clinical history of many of these illnesses are very varied, they may be grouped together into distinct related groupings because they share certain characteristics.

Materials and Procedures. Twenty patients were examined microbiologically for epidermal staphylococcus, gram-negative bacilli, Candida fungus, and non-hemolytic streptococcus. The aforementioned are more common in the paradental pocket and root canal, according to microbiologic studies. In this case, individuals with undamaged teeth and persistent generalized periodontitis are recommended to have their pulp extracted. The periodontal microbial complexes are red, orange, green, yellow, and purple.

Results and Results. The tooth and the periodontal (apical) aperture have developed a strong association as a result of their main mode of attachment. Research has shown that until the infection reaches the apical aperture, the pulp is not involved in the development of periodontal pockets in periodontal disorders. They might be found anywhere along the root. According to one research, extra canals were found in 17% of apical teeth, 9% of middle teeth, and 2% of upper third teeth. On the other hand, there are very few detrimental canal-related changes that affect the periodontium. The extra channels in the molars' furcation zone also aid in pulp and periodontal communication. Although there are 76% of auxiliary canals in this area, not all of them reach the bottom of the furcation or go through the whole thickness of the dentin. Another way to become infected is via dentin canals. In dentin tubes, tissue fluid (dentin) envelops odontoblasts and nerve fibers. The dentinal canals serve as channels for the spread of microbes in the case of carious lesions.

The Function of Microbiological Findings

Twenty individuals were the subject of a microbiological investigation that confirmed the disease's polymicrobial character by identifying the main microbial culprits found in the affected sites:

Particular Pathogens: Four important microbial types were shown to be common in the paradental pocket and root canal by the study: non-hemolytic streptococcus, gram-negative bacilli, Candida fungus, and epidermal staphylococcus.

Where the microbes are located: The idea of a common or linked microbial reservoir is supported by the presence of these bacteria in both the root canal and the paradental pocket, confirming the need of a therapy that targets both areas at the same time.

Complexes of Microbes: The identification of color-coded periodontal microbial complexes (red, orange, green, yellow, and purple) suggests the presence of complex microbial communities (biofilms) that fuel inflammation. The "red complex"—which contains *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, which was discussed in the overview—is often linked to the most severe types of periodontitis. These color codes indicate distinct groups of bacteria with differing degrees of pathogenicity.

Conclusion. Restoring the tooth's supporting structures and removing the microbiological component from the periodontium, pocket, and root canal system are essential components of a good therapy. The high frequency and complex pathogenesis of periodontitis, characterized by key microbial agents and distinct communication channels between the periodontal and endodontic spaces, necessitate a targeted, early, and comprehensive decontamination strategy focused on eliminating the infection from both the root canal and the surrounding tissues to ensure successful long-term outcomes.

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